

Global Research Publications on Open Data: A Scientometric Analysis

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ABSTRACT

Introduction- *Open Data is a new phenomenon in the research field, which is the next level of the open-access movement. In the current information age, data holds enormous value in any research to validate research findings.*

Purpose- *The purpose of the present study is to analyze the global research trends and patterns in the "Open Data" research using various Scientometric parameters.*

Research problem- *The number of bibliometric and scientometric studies on Open Data and relevant research topics are very limited and these studies are based on the WoS records. Hence, the authors planned to investigate the present study using the Open Data research literature from Scopus Data.*

Objective- *The key objective of this study is to analyze the research productivity and to identify the different patterns in the literature on "Open Data" research since from first publication as indexed in Scopus database.*

Methodology- *The authors analyzed 3252 bibliographic records indexed in the Scopus database up to 2021. The study used various scientometrics indicators and mathematical formulae to analyze these records to find parameters like year-wise publication and citation trends, degree of collaboration, collaborative co-efficient, collaboration index, most prolific authors, institutes involved in the research etc. The collected then fed into computer using CSV file format. Further, these records were analyzed using MS-Excel and VoSViewer.*

Findings- *The study found collaborative trends among the researchers and the highest number of publications as conference papers. The USA has contributed the highest number of papers. The Delft University of Technology, Netherlands is the most productive organization, and the top two contributors are affiliated with the same university.*

Keywords: Open Data; Scientometric Analysis; Research Data; Publication Trends; Research Patterns

INTRODUCTION

The global scholarly community is moving towards 'Open Access'. The term Open Access was coined in February 2002 at the Budapest Open Access Initiative, a public statement of principles relating to open access to the research literature. However, open access journals have existed since 1990s. However Open Access movement in publishing has seen rapid growth between 2000 and 2009. According to Laakso et al. (2011), only 20 open access journals existed, which reached 741 in

2000, by the year 2009 number of Open Access had reached 4767. According to ROAD, the Directory of Open Access scholarly Resources (2022), nearly 58,473 journals were registered as Open Access.

In the current information age, data holds enormous value in any research to validate research findings. Hence, the open access focus gradually included the data, and the Open Data movement began. According to the Open Data Handbook (2022), "Open data is data that can be freely used, reused and redistributed by anyone". Thus, the scholarly community has played a very important role in the creation and dissemination of open data for each other's benefit and the benefit of scientific progress and society in general.

Scientometrics analysis is the quantitative analysis of a particular scientific research area. It will help to critically review the growth, patterns and impact of the research publications concerned with the research area under study. Recent developments in visualization mapping tools have helped to validate a large amount of bibliographic data to analyze and understand thoroughly. Thus the current study on Open Data is conducted using the scientometric and visualization mapping methods.

LITERATURE STUDY

Very few qualitative studies are available to date on the scientometric assessment of research literature on "Open Data". Few are: Onyancha (2016) conducted a bibliometric study on open research data in Sub-Saharan Africa using the Data Citation Index, a part of WoS, for publications between 2009 and 2014. A total of 846 datasets were analyzed, which is 0.03 of world publications. Among Sub-Saharan African Countries, South Africa has contributed the highest i.e. 539 data records, followed by Kenya (121) and Cameroon (944). Among the institutions, South Africa's Council for Scientific and Industrial Research has published the highest number of datasets, and the maximum number of datasets belongs to the 'Genetics and Heredity' and 'Biochemistry/molecular biology' subject areas. Zhang, Hua and Yuan (2018) have conducted a bibliographic analysis of Open Data using the records retrieved from the Web of Science database. The study analyzed 1,045 records published from 1998 to 2016 and found only 9% of publications from 1998 to 2008 and 91% during 2009-2016. The authors analyzed the keywords using SciMAT visualization tool and found the highest number of publications in semantic web theme followed by the government data. The study also found the USA as the most productive country.

Corrales-Garay, Ortiz-de-Urbina-Criado and Mora-Valentín (2018) conducted a co-word analysis on open data research. The study analysed 1387 articles indexed in the WoS database published during 1978-2017. The study found exponential growth in research only after 2011. The authors identified the Open Data research as multidisciplinary, considering publications in several disciplines using the Co-word analysis. The study identified highly preferred journals and highly contributing authors in the open data research area. Gupta et al. (2020) studied scientometric analysis of linked data research published during 1996-2019, indexed in the Scopus database. The study analyzed 6700 records and found a 59.04% annual average growth rate. The authors also analyzed the subject-wise distribution of research papers and identified the most significant keywords. Mohamad, Sylvester and Campbell-Meier (2022) conducted a bibliometric study on Open Government Data. The study analyzed 524 documents indexed in the Scopus database, published between 2016 and 2020. The authors generated 54 keywords with a minimum five co-occurrence threshold. The study found four main categories, seven emerging topics and 34 subtopics and further discussed each category in detail. The study developed taxonomy for Open Government Data using the bibliometric mapping technique. Since the number of bibliometric and scientometric studies on Open Data and relevant research topics are very limited and these studies are based on the WoS records. The authors hence undertook the present study using the Open Data research literature from Scopus Data.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The key objective of this study is to analyze the research productivity and to identify the different patterns in the literature on "Open Data" research since from first publication as indexed in Scopus. The other objectives of the study are to:

1. identify the publication patterns in the Open Data research literature;
2. find the Degree of Collaboration (DC), Collaborative Coefficient (CC) and Collaboration Index (CI);
3. analyze the types of documents and subject-wise distribution of publications;
4. ascertain the top ten productive journals, prolific authors, institutions and countries; and
5. identify the most prominent keywords used in the research papers and the top five highly cited papers in the Open Data research literature.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

According to Scopus, a popular bibliographic database, the first indexed publication dates back to 1992. For the current study, 3252 bibliographic records were collected from Scopus database from 1992 to 2020 in the CSV (comma-separated values) file format. Further, these records were analyzed using MS-Excel and VoSViewer.

ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSIONS

Year-wise distribution of publications

Table 1 shows the year-wise distribution of "Open Data" publications, citations and average citations earned per paper. The first paper indexed in Scopus on "Open Data" was in 1992; however, until 2004, there were no regular publications. Since 2004, publications got momentum and started published regularly without any annual gap. Between 1992 and 2021, a total of 3252 publications on Open Data were indexed in Scopus. The highest (387) publications were recorded in 2018, followed by 2017 (376) and 2016 (368). Till 2018 research publications on Open Data have followed linear growth, after 2018 number of publications started declining year by year. The table also shows the citation distribution of research papers published each year. Research papers published in 2014 have received the highest (3997) citations, followed by 3891 (2017) and 3616 (2016). However, the publication in the year 2007 received the highest average citations per paper at 414.33 CPP, followed by 26.60 (2011) and 21.30 (2012). A total of 3252 research papers have received 30,574 citations since the first indexed publications in Scopus at 9.40 average citations per paper.

Table 1: Year-wise distribution of publications

YEAR	TP	TC	CPP
1992	1	3	3.00
1995	1	3	3.00
1996	3	33	11.00
2000	2	20	10.00
2001	1	7	7.00
2002	1	3	3.00
2004	3	27	9.00
2005	2	32	16.00
2006	5	65	13.00

2007	6	2486	414.33
2008	11	135	12.27
2009	11	142	12.91
2010	39	737	18.90
2011	68	1809	26.60
2012	125	2662	21.30
2013	207	2509	12.12
2014	279	3997	14.33
2015	302	2982	9.87
2016	368	3616	9.83
2017	376	3891	10.35
2018	387	2058	5.32
2019	365	1573	4.31
2020	346	1274	3.68
2021	343	510	1.49
Total	3252	30574	9.40

Degree of Collaboration (DC)

The formula to calculate the Degree of Collaboration (DC) proposed by Subramanyam (1983) is based on single-authored and multi-authored papers for the unit of time. Degree of Collaboration is a ratio of collaborative research papers in the overall publications. Table 2 provides the year-wise Degree of Collaboration in Open Data research publications. Among the 3252 research publications, 30 (0.92%) papers do not have an author, and among the remaining 541 (16.64%) are single-authored papers. The remaining 2681 (82.44%) research publications are by two or more collaborated authors, which indicate the multi-authors trends among the researchers on "Open Data". Overall, 0.83 Degree of Collaboration was recorded.

Table 2: Degree of Collaboration (DC)

Publication Year	No Authors	%	Single authored	%	Multi authored	%	Total (Ns + Nm)	Degree of collaboration
			(Ns)		(Nm)			
1992	0	0.00	0	0.00	1	0.04	1	1.00
1995	0	0.00	0	0.00	1	0.04	1	1.00
1996	1	3.33	0	0.00	2	0.07	2	1.00
2000	0	0.00	1	0.18	1	0.04	2	0.50
2001	0	0.00	0	0.00	1	0.04	1	1.00
2002	0	0.00	1	0.18	0	0.00	1	0.00
2004	0	0.00	1	0.18	2	0.07	3	0.67
2005	0	0.00	0	0.00	2	0.07	2	1.00
2006	0	0.00	0	0.00	5	0.19	5	1.00
2007	0	0.00	2	0.37	4	0.15	6	0.67
2008	0	0.00	6	1.11	5	0.19	11	0.45
2009	0	0.00	2	0.37	9	0.34	11	0.82

2010	0	0.00	5	0.92	34	1.27	39	0.87
2011	0	0.00	26	4.81	42	1.57	68	0.62
2012	3	10.00	24	4.44	98	3.66	122	0.80
2013	1	3.33	33	6.10	173	6.45	206	0.84
2014	2	6.67	49	9.06	228	8.50	277	0.82
2015	2	6.67	51	9.43	249	9.29	300	0.83
2016	5	16.67	56	10.35	307	11.45	363	0.85
2017	4	13.33	68	12.57	304	11.34	372	0.82
2018	3	10.00	73	13.49	311	11.60	384	0.81
2019	4	13.33	55	10.17	306	11.41	361	0.85
2020	4	13.33	50	9.24	292	10.89	342	0.85
2021	1	3.33	38	7.02	304	11.34	342	0.89
Total	30	100.00	541	100.00	2681	100.00	3222	0.83

Collaborative Coefficient (CC) and Collaboration Index (CI)

The authorship pattern in Table 3 shows that the number of publications by three-authored papers is dominated by 760 (23.37%) publications, followed by two authored papers with 727 (22.36%) publications and mega-authored, i.e., five or more authored papers with 703 (21.62%) publications. The Collaboration Coefficient (CC) of the research papers published on "Open Data" ranges between 0 and 0.81, with an average are 0.56. Ajiferuke et al. (1988) define Collaboration Coefficient as 'lies between 0 and 1, with 0 corresponding to single-authored papers, CC value is more than 0.5 indicates collaboration rate among the authors is found better'. Hence, the overall mean collaboration coefficient (0.56) during the study was higher than 0.5, implying the dominance of multiple-authored research papers on Open Data. A total of 11,891 authors are involved in publishing the 3,252 research papers on "Open Data". Lawani (1980) suggested a mathematical formula to calculate the Collaboration Index (CI), an average number of authors per paper for a particular unit of time. Hence, Collaboration Index for the overall research papers on "Open Data" is 3.82, i.e., the average number of authors who collaborated for each paper published on "Open Data".

Table 3: Collaborative Coefficient (CC) and Collaboration Index (CI)

Year	No Authors	Single Author	Two Authors	Three Authors	Four Authors	Five & above	Total	Collaboration Coefficient	Total Authors of Multi Authored Papers	Collaboration Index
1992	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0.75	4	4.00
1995	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0.75	4	4.00
1996	1	0	0	1	1	0	3	0.81	7	2.33
2000	0	1	0	0	1	0	2	0.38	4	2.50
2001	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0.67	3	3.00
2002	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0.00	0	1.00
2004	0	1	0	1	1	0	3	0.47	7	2.67
2005	0	0	1	1	0	0	2	0.58	5	2.50
2006	0	0	1	2	1	1	5	0.68	18	3.60
2007	0	2	1	1	0	2	6	0.46	22	4.00
2008	0	6	3	1	1	0	11	0.27	13	1.73
2009	0	2	5	0	2	2	11	0.51	28	2.73

2010	0	5	11	8	4	11	39	0.58	126	3.36
2011	0	26	14	12	5	11	68	0.41	162	2.76
2012	3	24	25	29	17	27	125	0.55	376	3.20
2013	1	33	43	58	37	35	207	0.56	672	3.41
2014	2	49	61	62	40	65	279	0.56	891	3.37
2015	2	51	62	74	47	66	302	0.56	965	3.36
2016	5	56	94	83	48	82	368	0.57	1240	3.52
2017	4	68	86	75	66	77	376	0.55	1181	3.32
2018	3	73	81	100	57	73	387	0.55	1177	3.23
2019	4	55	87	90	55	74	365	0.57	1140	3.27
2020	4	50	74	72	54	92	346	0.59	1294	3.88
2021	1	38	78	89	52	85	343	0.60	2552	7.55
Total	30	541	727	760	491	703	3252	0.56	11891	3.82

Distribution of Publications: Document type

Table 4 presents the document types of the literature published on Open Data. The publications (3,252) belong to thirteen document types. More than half of the literature published on Open Data were conference papers (1696, 52.15%), followed by Article (1161; 35.70%), Book Chapter (143; 4.40%) and Review (89; 2.74%). A large number of Conference papers usually indicate a new scope or idea in a research area. However, the highest number of citations was recorded for Articles (16,148), which indicate the importance and reach of journal articles, followed by Conference Papers (11,090) and Reviews (1937). The highest citations per paper were recorded in reviews (21.76), followed by the articles (13.91) and books (13.50), and recorded no citations for conference reviews.

Table 4: Distribution of Publications: Document type

DOCUMENT TYPE	TP	%	TC	CPP
Conference Paper	1696	52.15	11090	6.54
Article	1161	35.70	16148	13.91
Book Chapter	143	4.40	413	2.89
Review	89	2.74	1937	21.76
Note	55	1.69	383	6.96
Editorial	41	1.26	246	6.00
Letter	25	0.77	111	4.44
Erratum	11	0.34	10	0.91
Short Survey	9	0.28	99	11.00
Conference Review	8	0.25	0	0.00
Data Paper	8	0.25	56	7.00
Book	6	0.18	81	13.50
Total	3252	100.00	30574	9.40

Figure-1: Document type-wise distribution of publications

Subject-wise distribution of Publications

Open Data is an interdisciplinary research area. Hence, the research publications on Open Data were scattered across over 28 major subject areas in the Scopus database. Table 5 provides the top ten research subject areas where Open Data research is conducted according to its relevance. The highest number of research publications were shown in the Computer Science domain with 2158 (66.36%) research publications with 18,881 citations, followed by Social Sciences (818; 25.15%; 9412) and Mathematics (522, 16.05%; 6087). However, publications listed in Mathematics subject area have received the highest 11.66 citations per paper (CPP), followed by Social Sciences (11.51) and Environment Sciences (10.09).

Table 5: Subject-wise distribution of Publications

SUBJECT AREA	TP	TC	CPP	h-index
Computer Science	2158	18881	8.75	51
Social Sciences	818	9412	11.51	43
Mathematics	522	6087	11.66	28
Engineering	496	2714	5.47	26
Decision Sciences	283	2406	8.50	22
Business, Management and Accounting	237	2038	8.60	22
Earth and Planetary Sciences	175	895	5.11	14
Medicine	170	1378	8.11	20
Environmental Science	148	1494	10.09	19
Arts and Humanities	111	549	4.95	13

Figure-2: Subject-wise distribution of Publications

Top ten most productive journals

Out of 3252 research papers published on "Open Data", 1391 (42.77%) research papers were published in Journals as articles, editorials, letters, reviews, notes etc. These 1391 scholarly publications were published across 772 journals by the "Open Data" researchers. The data in table 6 found the *Government Information Quarterly* (published by Elsevier) to be the most preferred journal for publications with 23 (1.65%) publications, followed by the *Profesional De La Informacion* (18) and *Ejournal of Edemocracy and Open Government* (17). This trend shows that research literature on "Open Data" is not concentrated in one or two major journals; many journals accept these. However, it is also seen research literature published in *Government Information Quarterly* has received higher citations, i.e., 2060 (89.56 average citations per paper) and 20 h-index. Among the top ten most productive journals, two journals are published by MDPI and IOS Press, and different publishers publish the remaining six. Two journals are from the USA, Switzerland, and the Netherlands.

Table 6: Top ten most productive journals

Name of a Journal	Publisher	Country	TP	TC	h-index
<i>Government Information Quarterly</i>	Elsevier Ltd.	United Kingdom	23	2060	20
<i>Profesional De La Informacion</i>	El Profesional de la Informacion	Spain	18	223	10
<i>Ejournal of Edemocracy and Open Government</i>	Department for E-Governance and Administration	Austria	17	214	9
<i>IEEE Access</i>	IEEE Inc.	USA	13	210	5
<i>Sustainability Switzerland</i>	Springer Nature	Singapore	13	87	5
<i>ISPRS International Journal of Geo Information</i>	MDPI	Switzerland	12	100	5
<i>Information Switzerland</i>	MDPI	Switzerland	12	70	5
<i>Plos One</i>	Public Library of Science	USA	12	185	6
<i>Information Polity</i>	IOS Press	Netherlands	11	355	6
<i>Semantic Web</i>	IOS Press	Netherlands	11	420	8

Top ten most productive authors

The Open Data research literature published in 3252 articles was published by 9291 authors. Table 7 lists the top ten most productive authors. Marijn F.W.H.A. Janssen of Delft University of Technology, Delft has published maximum number of research papers on Open Data i.e. 55 (1.69%), followed by Anneke Zuiderwijk (48; 1.48%) from the same organisation and Adegboyega Ojo of Maynooth University, Maynooth (25, 0.77%). According to the number of citations attracted, Marijn F.W.H.A. Janssen leads with the highest, i.e. 2664 citations, followed by Anneke Zuiderwijk (2590) and Yannis K. Charalabidis of the University of the Aegean, Mytilene (1159). Two of the ten authors are affiliated with the Delft University of Technology, Delft and the University of the Aegean, Mytilene. According to the countries two authors are from the Netherlands, Austria, and Greece; one is from Ireland, Finland, Italy, and Germany. Figure 3 provides the co-authorship map of authors in research publications on Open Data. Out of 1562 authors with a minimum of two publications each, only 429 authors have collaborations with each other. The authors are divided into 30 clusters with 2069 links and 3307 link strengths. Authors with maximum collaborations are grouped in the same cluster; the size of the circle represents the magnitude of the number of papers, and the line represents the co-authorship strength. Marijn F.W.H.A. Janssen has links with 25 authors with 117 link strengths.

Table 7: Top ten productive authors

Name of author	Affiliation	Country	TP	TC	h-index
Marijn F.W.H.A. Janssen	Delft University of Technology, Delft	Netherlands	55	2664	22
Anneke Zuiderwijk	Delft University of Technology, Delft	Netherlands	48	2590	20
Adegboyega Ojo	Maynooth University, Maynooth	Ireland	25	265	9
Eero Hyvonen	Aalto University, Espoo	Finland	20	102	6
Yannis K. Charalabidis	University of the Aegean, Mytilene	Greece	19	1159	8
Sebastian Neumaier	Fachhochschule St. Polten, Sankt Polten	Austria	15	250	7
Axel Florian Polleres	Complexity Science Hub Vienna, Vienna	Austria	15	245	8
Jouni Tuominen	Aalto University, Espoo	Finland	15	80	5
Charalampos Alexopoulos	University of the Aegean, Mytilene	Greece	14	122	5
Vittorio Scarano	Università degli Studi di Salerno, Salerno	Italy	14	73	5
Ansgar Scherp	Universität Ulm, Ulm	Germany	14	110	6

Top ten most productive Countries

A study on country-wise research contribution to a particular research area helps to reveal the characteristics and research interest of the country as a single unit. A total of 138 countries participated in the research on Open Data, which shows an average of 29.83 publications per country. The USA has recorded the highest, i.e. 442 (13.59%) number of publications, followed by Italy (314; 9.66%) and Germany (311; 9.56%). It is also noteworthy to mention that eight of the top ten most productive countries in Open Data research are developed countries. Only two, i.e., Brazil and China, are developing countries. This indicates that developed countries concentrate research on Open Data than developing and least developed countries. India is ranked 19th position in Open Data research. Figure 4 provides the co-authorship map of countries in research publications on Open Data. Out of 94 countries with a minimum of two publications each, only 88 countries have collaborations. The countries are divided into 15 clusters with 625 links and 1850 link strength. The USA has 57 collaborating countries with 334 link strengths.

Table 9: Top ten most productive Countries

Country	TP	TC	h-index
United States	442	9089	41
Italy	314	2765	27
Germany	311	5521	31
United Kingdom	266	4249	33
Spain	251	1806	26
Netherlands	189	4680	34
France	154	1336	16
Japan	152	636	10
Brazil	125	532	12
Canada	116	1567	20
China	116	1393	18

Figure-4: Co-authorship map of highly-productive countries

Mapping of Keyword Co-occurrence

Across the 3252 research publications on Open Data, overall 5916 keywords were used. The keyword co-occurrence map visualizes the top 100 used author keywords that have appeared at least ten times in Open Data research literature. The top 100 keywords in the co-occurrence map are divided into nine different clusters based on the relevance in appearance with each other, with 959 links and 3211 link strengths. The thickness of the link between the keywords indicates the number of co-occurrences of the keywords in a publication together. Keyword co-occurrence visualization map determines the research hotspots in the Open Data research. Highly used keywords in the Open Data literature are Open Data (1086), linked open data (411), semantic web (190), linked data (186) and open government (111).

Figure-5: Mapping of Keyword Co-occurrence

Highly cited publications

Table 10 depicts the top five highly cited research publications indexed in the Scopus database among the Open Data literature. Among the 3252 research papers, two publications have received more than 1000 citations, and 35 have received more than 100 citations. Among the top five highly cited publications, three are articles, and one each are conference paper and review.

Table 10: Highly cited publications on Open Data

Author/s	Article Title	Year	Source	Citations
Auer S. et al. (6 Author)	DBpedia: A nucleus for a Web of open data	2007	Lecture Notes in Computer Science (including subseries Lecture Notes in Artificial Intelligence and Lecture Notes in Bioinformatics), V.4825 LNCS, pp.722-735	2367
Janssen M., Charalabidis Y. and	Benefits, Adoption Barriers and Myths of Open Data and Open	2012	Information Systems Management, V.29(4), pp.258-268	1002

Zuiderwijk A.	Government			
Reichman O.J., Jones M.B. and Schildhauer M.P.	Challenges and opportunities of open data in ecology	2011	Science, V.331(6018), pp.703-705	445
Zuiderwijk A. and Janssen M.	Open data policies, their implementation and impact: A framework for comparison	2014	Government Information Quarterly, V.31(1), pp.17-29	327
Piwowar H.A. and Vision T.J.	Data reuse and the open data citation advantage	2013	PeerJ, V.2013(1), e175	283

FINDINGS AND CONCLUSION

Open data is acting as a change agent in mainstream research activities. Open data helps the research community to validate the new research findings and brings greater transparency to research. Accessibility of open data has improved efficiency and reduced the research cost significantly. Open data has brought a new paradigm shift in research innovations. Thus, the current study helps to understand Open Data research's publication pattern and collaboration trends.

The study found that the research on Open Data rose over the last ten years. The adoption of 'Open Data' in publications still did not get space as a regular component with research publications. However, many funding agencies made it mandatory for the sponsored research publications to proactive sharing of research data and the publishers like IOP Publishing, PLOS, Springer Nature, Taylor & Francis have Open data sharing policy. The current scientometrics study on the "Open Data" research literature will help the researchers, policymakers, academicians, scientific community to identify the research trends and patterns. However, looking at the trends, there are ample opportunities to adopt the collaboration among the researchers and publish more journal articles on "Open Data".

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